

MODELING COMPLEXITIES IN THE PROCESS SIMULATION OF POLYMERIC COMPOSITE MATERIALS

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ABSTRACT

Simulation of the cure process for thermoset composite parts is now recognized as an important step in composite design. However, the material model development needed to support process simulation is a prodigious task, requiring complex models and testing to characterize chemical, thermal, mechanical, and thermo-mechanical responses of the material(s) of interest. The most important complicating factor is the evolving state of the resin material as it cures, necessitating the use of complex and strongly-interacting models, for which well-defined standard test procedures do not exist. In this paper we describe recent model development activities at the United States Air Force Research Laboratory (AFRL), and related experimental work, with emphasis on the challenges associated with defining, populating, and validating suitable models for cure process simulation. We review the underlying hypotheses for our current models, some of which are unconventional, and the difficulties involved in deriving appropriate property information from standard mechanical and thermo-mechanical tests. The need for greater flexibility in defining test procedures that are consistent with complex and unconventional response models is noted and discussed.

1 INTRODUCTION

Cure process simulation is now recognized as an essential step in the design of thermoset composite materials, allowing for more intelligent process specification and the design of appropriate tooling compensation. The resulting reductions in part rejection rates and tooling correction cycles are significant in terms of both time and expense, which in turn affect the feasibility and affordability of choosing a composite material [1]. Small-scale defects such as porosity and localized fiber wrinkling often originate in the earliest stages of manufacturing (layup, debulking, bagging) and are heavily influenced by highly variable and complex factors such as human handwork, material variations, manufacturing environment, and complex multiphase flow behavior. These problems pose the most difficult challenges for analytical simulations and have received the least attention. Macro-scale defects, including part distortion, delamination, ply-scale wrinkling, and reduced strength or life caused by excessive residual stress, are more directly associated with the resin cure process, and have been the subject of numerous recent investigations [2-5]. Despite the significant progress made in the analysis of autoclave and out-of-autoclave cure processes since the earliest “ $\alpha\Delta T$ ” models (e.g., [6]) based on stress-free temperature assumptions, accurate simulation of the curing process remains a challenging task, due primarily to the complexity of the material characterization and response modeling. Larger-scale defects occurring during cure also arguably represent the most significant manufacturing issues because of their cost and scheduling consequences, which include part rejection, tool redesign, and part machining, repair or redesign to correct for interference or excessive fit-up stress. This paper focuses on the challenges engendered in the task of defining reliable material

models for simulating the coupled chemical, thermal, and mechanical response of polymeric composites during the curing stage of processing.

2 MATERIAL MODEL OVERVIEW AND HYPOTHESES

In this paper we focus on the simulation of an autoclave or out-of-autoclave curing process, beginning with an uncured prepreg layup or resin-infused preform. The essential models needed for this stage of a composite cure cycle simulation are cure kinetics, thermal expansion, cure shrinkage, conductivity, heat capacity, density, and stress-deformation behavior (elasticity, viscoelasticity, plasticity, and viscosity). As the resin cures, its state changes continuously and irreversibly at a rate which varies with position, with physical properties being functions of both the degree of cure and the current temperature, and possibly their rates of change with time. Therefore, model properties used must be determined as functions of these two parameters from tests during which, at elevated temperature, the degree of cure may change continuously.

Recent cure modeling research at AFRL includes the development of response models based on the following general hypotheses:

(1) Key properties such as thermal expansion, cure shrinkage, modulus, and viscosity, which are strong functions of both temperature and degree of cure, may be characterized in terms of a single variable T_R , the reduced temperature:

$$T_R = T / T_g(x) - 1 \quad (1)$$

Here x represents the degree of cure, and T_g the glass transition temperature; $T_R < 0$ is the glassy region, and $T_R > 0$ is the rubbery region.¹ This hypothesis reflects commonly-observed behavior of polymeric composites, with the effect of increasing temperature being similar to that of decreasing degree of cure, and vice versa.

(2) The most significant relaxation behavior of the polymer, in terms of residual stress development, occurs near and above the glass transition, and may be modelled as irreversible, time-dependent plastic flow. This relaxation also may result in a change in the reference temperature for thermal expansion (equivalently, the “stress-free temperature”) at a point. Accordingly, we represent the thermo-mechanical behavior of the polymer using a “unified” [7] viscoplastic model, with thermal expansion defined using a tangent thermal expansion coefficient without a fixed reference temperature.

The resulting chemo-thermo-mechanical material model is, in one-dimensional form,

$$\dot{\epsilon} = \frac{\dot{\sigma}}{E} + \frac{\sigma}{\eta} + \alpha \dot{T} + \beta \dot{x} \quad (2)$$

The four terms on the right side of (2) represent elastic, viscoplastic, thermal expansion, and cure shrinkage contributions to the total strain rate. The properties E (modulus), η (viscosity), α (thermal expansion coefficient, or CTE), and β (shrinkage coefficient) are each assumed to be a function of reduced temperature. To produce the sharp transitions observed in the neighbourhood of the glass transition, we represent each property (or its logarithm) in the form (see Fig. 1)

$$p(T_R) = \frac{A}{1 + e^{b(T_R - c)}} + f T_R + g \quad (3)$$

Parameters (A,b,c,f,g) control, respectively: the range of property values; the transition rate near $T_R=0$; the location of the glassy-rubbery transition; the slope or rotation of the curve; and the mean property value. Parameter values are determined by numerical optimization to minimize the sums of squared differences between the model and measured data, with appropriate bound constraints imposed.

¹ Glass transition temperatures determined by different test methods often disagree. Since only the reduced temperature appears in the property models, the actual value of T_g does not affect the properties. However, the calculation of T_g and reduced temperature in the data reduction and the simulation must be consistent.

Figure 1. Modulus, viscosity, CTE, and shrinkage as functions of reduced temperature. Properties shown are for Cycom® 5320-1, a toughened epoxy resin.

Constraints are imposed on the resulting properties to ensure that $\beta \leq 0$, and to limit the values of η for numerical reasons. A fully three-dimensional form of the elastic-viscoplastic (E-VP) model is:

$$\dot{\sigma}_{ij} = C_{ijmn} \left(\dot{\epsilon}_{mn} - \frac{\sigma'_{mn}}{\eta} - \alpha \dot{T} \delta_{mn} - \beta \dot{x} \delta_{mn} \right) \quad (4)$$

Here $\sigma'_{mn} = \sigma_{mn} - \frac{1}{3} \sigma_{kk} \delta_{mn}$ are deviatoric stress components, representing the stresses associated with shape distortion at constant volume. It is important to note that the coefficient α in (2) and (4) is a *tangent* CTE, rather than the *secant* value typically used in engineering models. The tangent CTE α and shrinkage coefficient β are defined in terms of the rate of change of the thermal free expansion strain,

$$\dot{\epsilon}^{(th)} = \left(\frac{\partial \epsilon^{(th)}}{\partial T} \right)_x \dot{T} + \left(\frac{\partial \epsilon^{(th)}}{\partial x} \right)_T \dot{x} = \alpha \dot{T} + \beta \dot{x} \quad (5)$$

The more familiar secant CTE α_s is defined as the ratio of the total free thermal expansion strain to the temperature difference from a fixed reference value, such that

$$\epsilon^{(th)} = \alpha_s (T - T_0) \quad (6)$$

The two CTE values are related by

$$\alpha = \alpha_s + \frac{\partial \alpha_s}{\partial T} (T - T_0) \quad (7)$$

Most engineering calculations use the secant CTE value, since it allows the mechanical strain to be separated from the thermal strain during stress calculation, provided the assumption of a fixed strain-free reference temperature is valid. The use of the tangent CTE in the models of Eqs. (2) and (4) allows for the possibility that stress relaxation at a temperature above T_g produces a rise in the stress-free temperature, which seems particularly likely as the resin changes state during cure.

It is worth noting also that the viscosity η in Eq. (4) is not equivalent to the property measured in a simple viscometry test, where it is assumed that the resistance of the specimen to deformation is due solely to viscous behavior. In the viscoplastic model, resistance to deformation occurs both in the form of elastic stiffness, related to reversible strain, and viscosity, which is associated with irreversible (dissipative) strain.

For cure cycle simulation, instantaneous composite properties must be homogenized from the constituent material properties. Currently we use micromechanical finite element models at individual material points [3] for homogenizing the mechanical (modulus, viscosity) and thermo-mechanical

(expansion, shrinkage) properties, and analytical methods [8] for combining the constituent thermal properties. In what follows, we focus on the development of the resin material models only.

3. MATERIAL PROPERTY EXPERIMENTS AND DATA REDUCTION

Basic thermal properties of the resin (density, conductivity, specific heat) can be determined accurately through standard test methods, although kinetics and T_g models, which allow for estimation of the instantaneous T_g and T_R of the specimen during the standard tests, are needed for interpretation of the measured properties. Here we limit discussion to the properties mentioned above that appear in the thermo-mechanical model (modulus, viscosity, CTE, and cure shrinkage coefficient), and the T_g model needed for the interpretation of the property test data.

A typical test and data reduction sequence is shown in Fig. 2. Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) is used to determine the total heat of reaction per unit mass, which is needed for specification of the internal heat generation in model predictions. The DSC data also provide a basis for estimating the degree of cure (or equivalently, T_g) of samples from partially-cured plaques used in subsequent testing. The T_g model is needed for design of thermo-mechanical analysis (TMA) test temperature profiles that isolate regions of thermo-mechanical behavior that are dominated by thermal expansion (e.g., temperature ramps causing thickness change accompanied by little or no advancement of the cure reaction) or cure shrinkage (e.g., constant temperature holds near or above T_g , during which significant crosslinking and associated shrinkage occurs, while thermal expansion is limited to small increments caused by the dependence of CTE on degree of cure). The TMA data are combined with the T_g model to populate the CTE and shrinkage coefficient models. Finally, mechanical rheometry tests are performed, which may include monotonic loading, load-unload cycling, creep under constant load, stress relaxation at constant strain, or combinations of these, at various temperatures and degrees of cure. The rheometric test data are analyzed (using the T_g , CTE, and shrinkage models) to determine instantaneous modulus and viscosity as functions of reduced temperature.

Figure 2. Sequential use of property models in data reduction process.

The reasoning behind the test and analysis sequence outlined above is sound, but the challenges are significant. Below we outline a few of the more persistent issues present in applying this process to composite cure simulation.

3.1 Calorimetry – chemical kinetics and glass transition models

Initial calorimetry tests provide heat-of-reaction information, which is used to describe the state of the polymer as crosslinking occurs during cure. All subsequent property data are indexed using these results, to quantify the state of the material, and any uncertainty in this model propagates to the remaining thermo-mechanical and mechanical properties of the resin. One can argue that the role of the degree of cure as an independent variable is completely phenomenological, and that errors in the DSC-based models are unimportant assuming that the model is applied consistently throughout the data reduction process. However, a more fundamental understanding of the connection between

chemistry and the resulting physical properties is ultimately what will render the cure simulation problem tractable, eliminating the data-intensive approach that is required at present.

A key issue in the interpretation of DSC data is the creation of a baseline curve isolating the heat of reaction from other heat flow recorded in the test. Baseline curves may be defined using tangents to the heat flow curve, connecting minimum points, or other heuristics, all of which may produce significantly different total heats of reaction and models of degree of cure (as measured by the fraction of total reaction heat). Fig. 3 shows a typical heat flow trace, with one possible choice of baseline curves shown, based on local minimum points. Overlapping reaction peaks in the heat flow history trace further complicate the selection of a meaningful baseline by obscuring what might otherwise be suitable key points for use in establishing the baseline. It is important to note that, in developing model properties, we implicitly assume that the relationship between degree of cure (and expected properties) and the fraction of total heat of reaction expended is identical for all time-temperature histories. Selecting a baseline that ensures this assumption is satisfied, at least approximately, in practice is a complex task that requires thorough knowledge of the reactions specific to the polymer of interest, and cannot be automated at present.

Figure 3. DSC heat of reaction baseline determination.

Complex aerospace resins present additional challenges in interpreting the DSC trace. The transition from imidization to crosslinking for imides may not be clear-cut, which is important in view of the fact that phenomenological imidization models are typically less advanced than those for crosslinking. If the imidization process is not modeled directly, the initial degree of cure must be estimated in the model data, and the mass and volume change associated with imidization, which may be significant, must be reflected in the subsequent modeling. Similarly, multicomponent chemistries and tougheners can lead to overlapping reactions making the baseline onset and endset selection challenging. During crosslinking, the precise nature of the chemical reactions is not fully understood (e.g., primary versus secondary reactions happening simultaneously), making the expected energy release more uncertain as well.

3.2 Thermomechanical analysis – thermal expansion and cure shrinkage models

Strains induced by linear thermal expansion, which are reversible, and those due to cure shrinkage, which are irreversible, appear in the mechanical models as debits from the total strain rate. In other words, these changes in volume or length cause no stress unless they are inhibited either by surrounding material or by fixturing constraints. The TMA experiment attempts to characterize both of these responses by heating a specimen with as little constraint as possible. CTE and shrinkage strains can be separated approximately according to the terms in Eq. (5) above. When the temperature is changing, but low enough that no significant crosslinking occurs, the degree of cure changes slowly or not at all, and thickness changes are caused primarily by thermal expansion, since $\alpha = (\partial\varepsilon / \partial T)_x$. If the temperature is held constant, and is high enough to advance the degree of cure, the effect of shrinkage dominates, $\beta = (\partial\varepsilon / \partial x)_T$. A useful test sequence then consists of a series of temperature

increases, holds, and decreases as in Fig. 4. The test sequence for a given material is designed using the kinetics model to predict features like the duration of the high-temperature holds, which is selected to allow significant cure advancement at constant temperature (thereby isolating the cure shrinkage coefficient), and to permit the change in degree of cure to decay sufficiently that dimensional changes during the succeeding temperature down-ramp are dominated by thermal contraction. In the sequence shown in Fig. 4, the isothermal holds are two hours long, and the cooling segments are generally 60°C. In many cases, the TMA data are sufficiently noiseless that nearly all of the data can be included in an optimization procedure that exercises the actual model iteratively to identify a suitable system of thermal expansion and cure shrinkage properties, subject to limitations noted below.

Figure 4. Typical TMA test sequence.

The most serious issues with TMA testing arise because it is difficult to fabricate specimens with very low degree of cure, and because of lateral spreading of the specimen at higher T_R (high temperature or low degree of cure), which causes measured thickness changes to overestimate the actual cure shrinkage. This problem is serious because both the (non-uniform) lateral flow and the actual cure shrinkage are permanent deformations, which are impossible to separate based on the test data or from pre- and post-test measurements. The need to start at intermediate degrees of cure also means that some of the total cure shrinkage will not be observed in the test. This omission is disappointing, but not necessarily critical from a modeling perspective, since the shrinkage that does occur when the specimen is relatively uncured likely contributes little to the final residual stress state.

Initial settling of the specimen and platens is a further issue, but one which can be resolved by testing multiple replicates. Figure 5 shows a series of TMA traces for a single material, at the same initial degree of cure, exposed to identical temperature histories. During the initial thermal cycle, variations in settling of the specimen and fixture yield a series of strain curves with variations on the order of 100 percent; if the curves are aligned at the start of the next thermal cycle, they are mostly indistinguishable from each other. However, we do not know which of the curves is most free of errors caused by the early-time behavior. Since the initial settling and lateral spreading of the test specimen are irreversible processes, the data obtained for cure shrinkage are most strongly affected.

During the process of property identification, depending on the assumptions made about shrinkage prior to the test, and on the way the test data are adjusted to account for variability, results for optimization of the cure shrinkage properties can vary significantly, and must be constrained to ensure uniqueness of the results. Currently, we measure the actual specimen thickness before and after the TMA experiment. The resulting total strain estimate allows the final strain value (representing only the shrinkage occurring in the degree-of-cure range of the test) to be anchored prior to the property identification process. This is a good solution in concept, but the direct measurements of the thickness produce strain estimates with a fair amount of variation, and which still contain errors caused by lateral spreading of the specimen at low degree of cure, as noted earlier. This problem occurs even when the preload levels are reduced to extremely low levels (0.01 Newtons for the case in Figure 5).

Figure 5. TMA strain measurements for several nominally identical specimens.

It should be noted that equivalent thermo-mechanical measurements also can be performed using volume dilatometry [3]. The resulting data often exhibits greater scatter than data from the TMA, and is therefore difficult to interpret unambiguously. Methods also exist for calibrating cure shrinkage models based on more complicated specimen configurations such as bi-material beams [5]; however, such processes require more elaborate modeling, typically three-dimensional finite element models, which may affect the resulting property information.

3.3 Rheological testing – modulus and viscosity models

Rheometer tests provide mechanical response information needed to define modulus, viscosity, and flow stress model parameters. Mechanical characterization is complicated by two main factors. The first of these is the broad variation in properties within the behavior regions of interest: modulus values for a single resin may range, with temperature and degree of cure, from tens of MPa to a few GPa, and viscosities may vary by several orders of magnitude in a single test. Load cells with the sensitivity needed for accurate measurements when the material stiffness is extremely low often do not possess the capacity for testing the same material at lower temperature and high degree of cure, and vice versa. Fig. 6 shows an example of the striking variation in quasi-static mechanical response of a resin tested at a range of reduced temperatures slightly smaller than that experienced by the material in a typical cure process. Since the viscosity parameters needed for the mechanical models are those consistent with elastic-viscoplastic response, as opposed to the pure fluid viscosity that controls resin flow prior to gelation, inaccurate modulus values also contribute to error in determining the viscosity parameters.

Figure 6. Stress-strain behavior of a resin at various reduced temperatures.

Additional challenges are associated with the test procedures used to populate complex mechanical models for cure process simulation. Traditional mechanical testing of structural polymers is aimed largely at determining elastic constants, frequency response, damping properties, and viscoelastic

time-temperature shift data. Cure processes involve high nonlinearity at extremely low deformation rates, so that tests involving rate effects are not useful. Even small segments of a test performed at high rates can bias a dataset so that the use of numerical optimization for property identification, based on the actual material model of interest, is either impossible, or requires extensive editing of the test data and specification of artificial initial conditions.

Ideally, a mechanical test is designed with a model in mind; for the process modeller, the most common approach is to perform standard tests, and tune the material model using part-level models rather than material point calculations. This issue is particularly acute in the context of extracting viscosity data from mechanical tests. For the model in Eqs. (2) and (5) above, stress is associated with both elastic and viscous behavior, and these contributions must be distinguished from one another to isolate appropriate properties. If the stress dependence of the viscosity model is changed; for example:

$$\dot{\epsilon} = \frac{\dot{\sigma}}{E} + \frac{\sigma^n}{\eta} + \alpha \dot{T} + \beta \dot{x} \quad (8)$$

the meaning, and even the units, of the viscosity coefficient change accordingly. If a yield threshold σ_y is introduced, and the viscous dissipation is proportional to an overstress $\langle \sigma - \sigma_y \rangle$ to accommodate the behavior in Fig. (6) at intermediate reduced temperature, the significance and the value of the viscosity change. Currently, standard test procedures do not address such issues, and provide less-than-ideal support for defining customized test sequences tailored for non-traditional material models.

4. ANALYTICAL RESULTS

This section briefly presents some representative process simulation results, and discusses the role of accurate property information in achieving good engineering accuracy. Many of our studies to date have been based on angle bracket specimens (Fig. 7), which are perhaps the simplest configuration that illustrates the role of the interacting effects of thermal expansion, cure shrinkage, and process parameters on composite part distortion. Experimental and analytical investigations performed using this geometry include a full design of experiments study involving gelation temperature, ramp rate, and integrated versus freestanding postcure [10], and additional variations using modified ply layups, part thicknesses, bend radii, and materials [11].

Figure 7. Finite element model of angle bracket on tool, and map of spring-in angles.

In the Abaqus [12] analyses, one solid element per ply is used, since the objective is to predict macroscopic residual stress and spring-in of the part. The kinetics, heat transfer, stress-deformation, thermal expansion, and shrinkage models are introduced in a system of user-supplied subroutines that are called as needed during the solution. The integration points of each element are also material sampling points; at each such point, a separate micromechanical finite element model is used to combine and homogenize the composite material response near the point. The overall finite element

solution uses only composite-level, homogeneous stresses, while the micromechanical models at each sampling point solve for fiber and matrix stresses, including elastic, viscoplastic, thermal, and shrinkage effects. The kinetics model is applied at each point to track local degree of cure, and apply individual models for the material properties of interest.

The material models discussed earlier, and the finite element model described above, have been used to make predictions for numerous bracket configurations of interest, to develop an improved understanding of the effects of process variables, material properties, modeling assumptions, and numerical solution techniques. The part consists of a 16-ply laminate, $[45/90/-45/0]_{2S}$, made from Cycom® 5320-1/IM7 prepreg, processed with eight different cure cycles, designated 1a through 4b. The ‘a’ cycles use integrated postcure, and the ‘b’ cycles use freestanding (out of autoclave) postcure. Low cycle numbers (1,2) indicate a low gelation point (93.3°C) and high cycle numbers (3,4) indicate a higher gelation point (135°C). Even-numbered cycles (2,4) use a slower temperature ramp rate ($0.33^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$), and odd-numbered cycles (1,3) use a higher ramp rate ($1.33^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$).

In all cases, the legs of the bracket tend to spring inward, although the nature of the observed spring-in varies: some processes produce high spring-in near the spine of the bracket, while the legs splay out slightly, while others exhibit more moderate spring-in near the bend, with the legs curving inward. The amount of spring-in varies along the length of the brackets, by varying degrees. For brevity, here we will focus on the spring-in measured at the (trimmed) ends of the legs, at the center line of the long direction of the bracket (see Fig. 7).

Figure 8 shows a comparison of measured and predicted spring-in angles for all eight processing conditions described above. The diagonal line at the center represents zero error, and the parallel lines on either side of the diagonal represent 0.5-degree differences between measured and predicted values.

Figure 8. Bracket spring-in predictions for cure cycles with varying ramp rates, gelation temperatures, and postcure methods.

While absolute accuracy is always a modeling goal, uncertainty in experimental conditions, material parameters, and model approximations always introduce unpredictable variation in either measured or predicted response, as described in the first half of this paper. Therefore, the ability of the model to predict behavior *trends* correctly is just as important as absolute accuracy. Accurate trends indicate that the correct physics are present in the model, which means that the model is useful for assessing the effects of changes in the part, the tooling, or process parameters. The various cure cycles in Figure 8 are labeled to permit easy assessment of the trend predictions: parameter changes should produce correct increments in response, reflected by changes in distortion parallel to the diagonal line in Figure 8. Pairs of results from which individual trends can be examined are listed in Table 1. The trends predicted in Figure 8 are quite reliable for all process parameters, are generally overpredicting by 0.1-0.2 degrees, and are highly accurate for most combinations (with cycles 2a and 3b being the

exception). Therefore, we conclude that the computational and material models may be used with confidence to predict the effect of changes in key process parameters on distortion of the final part.

Table 1. Trend Comparisons

Parameter	Compare	Cases
Ramp rate	Low or high pairs	(1a, 2a); (1b, 2b); (3a, 4a); (3b, 4b)
Gelation temperature	Odd or even pairs	(1a, 3a); (2a, 4a); (1b, 3b); (2b, 4b)
Postcure method	a-b pairs	(1a, 1b); (2a, 2b); (3a, 3b); (4a, 4b)

Sensitivity of the model predictions to parameter errors, due to experimental or material variability in combination with uncertainty in data reduction procedures, is an important issue, as was mentioned earlier. Below we present a few results from property sensitivity calculations using the bracket spring-in the problem presented above. Sensitivity results for cure cycle 3a (autoclave process with high ramp rate and high gelation temperature) are shown in Figure 9. The left chart shows the sensitivity of the predicted final spring-in angle to five-percent variations in the nominal magnitude of the four properties in Figure 1; the right chart shows the effect of shifting the glassy-to-rubbery transition of each property curve left ($c-0.05$) or right ($c+0.05$) by an increment of 0.05 in reduced temperature.

Figure 9. Sensitivity of spring-in prediction to (a) property value; (b) transition point 'c'.

The overall magnitude of the modulus and viscosity obviously have a significant effect on residual stress and part distortion predictions (although the modulus sensitivity is relatively low for this example). However, the magnitudes of the cure shrinkage and CTE are equally important, since the five percent perturbations used in Figure 9 represent a relatively insignificant variation in these two properties. The experimental challenges in spreading and settling of the TMA specimens noted earlier can cause cure shrinkage to be overestimated by *a factor of two or more*, not a mere five percent, and would result in more than an order of magnitude variation in CS in Figure 9 (a).

Transition points for modulus and viscosity, whose sensitivities are shown in the right-hand plot of Figure 9, are relatively difficult to determine accurately, since the variability of the test data is highest near T_g . This is indeed unfortunate, since the relative positions of the modulus and viscosity transition points (see Figure 1) is one of the most important controlling factors in predicting part distortion. The corresponding transitions for cure shrinkage and CTE exhibit less scatter and can be determined relatively accurately.

The opposite trends associated with the shift point 'c' for modulus and viscosity are worthy of comment, since they reflect the differing roles in these two properties in controlling the residual stress development. This transition point represents the value of reduced temperature at the center of the transition between glassy (stiff) and rubbery (soft) behaviour. Increasing c moves the entire property curve to the right, extending the glassy region to higher reduced temperatures. For the viscosity, which controls stress relaxation at high T_R , the effect of increasing c_η is to reduce the region within which significant relaxation can occur during high-temperature holds, generally raising the residual stress level. The modulus controls the stress associated with reversible (elastic) strains, but also drives

stress relaxation, since the viscous strain rate is proportional to the stress. Lowering c_E can reduce stress relaxation by delaying the development of higher stresses that in turn drive the stress relaxation. Figure 10 shows this effect, in terms of the time history of fiber-direction stress at a point in the center of the bracket, near the bend, and at the outer surface. The red line shows the response for nominal property values, and the dotted lines show the corresponding stress history for increased viscosity (green), for c_η shifted right (orange), and for c_E shifted left (blue). The most significant effect occurs in the highest-temperature hold, where all three of these perturbations produce increasing stress in varying degrees, with the compressive stress remaining higher than the nominal case thereafter. The effect of higher viscosity is easy to understand, since the usual amount of stress relaxation does not occur during the hold. In the case of the left-shifted modulus curve, the modulus lags the nominal value, causing a lag in the start of relaxation, and increased stress through the final hold and cooldown.

Figure 10. Effect of property changes on residual stress evolution.

In practice, typical uncertainties in the absolute magnitude of the modulus, viscosity, cure shrinkage, and CTE, and their dependence on reduced temperature, can be responsible for errors on the order of 100 percent in part distortion predictions. The sensitivity calculations confirm that *the material property parameters that affect the residual stress and part distortion predictions most significantly are those most challenging to determine accurately* in characterization experiments.

5. CONCLUSIONS

Composite process simulation has progressed significantly in recent years, but still poses many serious challenges, mostly related to characterization and modeling of continuously evolving materials. This paper seeks to provide some perspective on the complexity and sources of variability in the methods we use, particularly with reference to measured data. We have reviewed a few of these problems in the context of our own current modeling activities. As always, numerous opportunities exist to improve our methodologies for testing, data interpretation, property identification, and modeling, but the nature of these improvements changes with time. Not that long ago, the prediction of residual stress and part distortion required only moduli and thermal expansion coefficients. We now put a much finer point on our analyses, using elaborate models based on complex multiphysics. The information needed to populate these increasingly complex models and our ability to measure and interpret that data are now the most important limiting factors in our predictive ability.

Given the complexity and inherent variability of the materials we use, we will never achieve, and should not expect, perfection in our models. The utility of the models lies in their ability to predict trends, to guide us in the right direction, and to reveal the important variables and their effects on the engineering task at hand, provided the correct physics are included in them. A second important observation based on this review is that experimental methods are strongly oriented toward property characterization of polymers and composites in their post-cure state, leaving significant gaps in our

ability to extract reliable physical and mechanical properties from experiments in which the material state is continually evolving. In the short term, data acquisition software extensions and instrument design improvements for polymeric material test systems are sorely needed to permit more precise and continuous control of test conditions to accommodate complex material behavior and models, to better support the growing interest in, and importance of, composite process modeling.

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